

Assessing Spatio-Temporal and Process Controls on Anthropogenic Landforms with Landscape Evolution Models

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Infrastructure systems upon which modern society depends are constructed within landscapes reshaped continuously by natural processes. Large-scale civil infrastructure works are also significant terraforming activities resulting in anthropogenic landscapes. Indigenous landscapes resulting from centuries of occupation also contain anthropogenic terraforms, and possess sacred sites and geological/geomorphic features considered fundamental to community cultural and spiritual identity. These anthropogenic landscapes are subject to long-term erosion and sedimentation processes that pose risks to the functioning of critical infrastructure and preservation of cultural heritage sites, and projected climate and land use changes may exacerbate these risks.

Landscape evolution models (LEMs) numerically simulate Earth surface processes and are used to study long-term landscape change. Most applications project transformations over millennia, reconstructing past events or predicting future conditions. While these models identify geomorphic trends over a range of spatio-temporal scales, they rarely determine the timing erosion and sedimentation will impact engineered landforms or landscapes important to Indigenous peoples. Advancing LEMs to address these spatio-temporal and process-based uncertainties is essential for improving the predictive accuracy of geoforecasting, and understanding landscape responses to environmental change.

This study employs LEMs using the Landlab platform, a Python-based framework designed for simulating Earth surface processes using Digital Elevation Models. By incorporating site-specific geomorphic knowledge, we model the unique surface processes influencing landscape evolution at each selected location. Our primary objective is to determine the timing at which specific points of interest will be affected by landscape change (erosion and sedimentation). To identify dominant processes, we systematically manipulate key parameters, holding certain variables constant to isolate their individual impacts. By iteratively adjusting these parameters, we aim to refine our understanding of the interactions between erosion, deposition, and hydrological dynamics, ultimately enhancing the predictive capabilities of landscape evolution models to determine the longevity of engineered landforms and inform long-term management of Indigenous landscapes.

Keywords: Landscape Evolution Modelling, Infrastructure, Indigenous Landscapes